

THE CLAIM LETTER AND FEATURES OF ITS TEXT

Nadir Ramazanov

Tashkent State University of Law

Head of the Department of Uzbek Language and Literature

doctor of philosophy (PhD) in philological sciences,

associate professor

It is known that service correspondence is divided into the following types according to its characteristics and the function it performs:

1. Letters requiring a response (claim letters, request letters, request letters).
2. Letters that do not require a reply letter (attachment letter, confirmation letter, reminder letter, information letter, guarantee letter, etc.).

Claim letters and their meaning

The letters stating the demands and objections of a certain institution against another office or transport organizations are called claim letters. Claim letters are drawn up in order to protect one's legal rights and interests in case of non-fulfillment of contracts concluded for the delivery of goods, construction works, rent, cargo transportation and other similar works. Claim letters generally seek compensation for damages caused by the breaching party.

The main required parts of the claim letters are:

1. Name and address of the applicant institution.
2. Date of writing of the letter and serial number.
3. Name and address of the institution receiving the claim.
4. The value of the claim.
5. The text of the letter.
6. List of applications (indicating the number of pages).
7. Signature of Official(s).

Usually, claim letters are prepared in triplicate. The 1st copy of the letter is left to the guilty party, and the 2nd copy is left to the plaintiff. If the guilty institution refuses to fulfill the requirements specified in the letter of claim, the 3rd copy of the letter shall be attached to the claim and submitted to the court or arbitration. In claim letters, the evidence, instructions and expert report, acceptance certificate, sales documents, etc., which justify and confirm the claimant's claim, must be attached to the letter and their list should be indicated.

Claim letters shall be accompanied by:

1. Freight cargo (railway cargo, air fleet cargo, truck cargo, etc.).
2. Sales documents (in case of partial loss and damage of cargo).
3. Certificate of acceptance of cargo for transportation (in case of total loss of cargo).
4. Document showing the list and price of the goods (goods) sent, payment request, invoices, document issued for sending the product.
5. The amount of the settlement of the claim (such calculations are attached only if they are not indicated in the text itself).
6. Documents that, in the opinion of the claimant, can confirm the validity of the claim.

The main issue in writing a letter of claim is the correct formulation of its text.

6 components of the text of the claim letter:

1. The first paragraph. History of the situation / situation (a contract concluded between two parties and its main terms).
2. The second paragraph. Payment actions performed in connection with the contract (date, number and amount of the payment order confirming the transfer of money from the bank account number).
3. The third paragraph. Information about goods delivered under the contract (shipment date, number and quantity of delivered goods).

4. The fourth paragraph. Information about undelivered inventory under the contract (amount and amount of remaining undelivered inventory).

5. The fifth paragraph. Deadlines for the performance of the contract (requirements by which date the obligations under the contract must be fully fulfilled).

6. The sixth paragraph. Sanction part (if obligations under the contract are not fulfilled by the specified period, further actions, legal documents and their relevant articles are indicated).

In short, pleadings are important documents for future lawyers to master. Because this letter has procedural significance and is an important means of resolving disputes peacefully. According to the procedural rules, filing a lawsuit without trying to resolve the conflict situation between the two parties peacefully by writing a letter of claim may cause the courts to become overloaded with work. Therefore, the best way to resolve disputes is through lawsuits. Forming the text part of the application form by the students is problematic. Because it is in the text part that the history of the occurrence of the claim situation, payment actions carried out under the contract, information about the goods delivered under the contract, information about the goods not delivered under the contract, deadlines for the execution of the contract and sanctions are reflected.

References

1. Ramazonov N.N. Davlat tilida ish yuritish va akademik yozuv: o‘quv qo‘llanma. – Toshkent: TDYU, 2023.

2. Mahmudov N. va b. Davlat tilida ish yuritish (9-nashri). – Toshkent, 2020.

3. Ish yuritish: Amaliy qo‘llanma. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi nashriyoti, 2017.

4. Bozorova N., Shamsitdinova M. GHAFUR GHULAM’S CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF MUQIMI’S WORK //CURRENT

RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 06. – С. 38-43.

5. Bozorova, N., & Madaliev, Y. K. (2023). GHAFUR GHULAM'S ARTISTIC PRINCIPLE IN ILLUMINATING THE TRUTH OF THE TIME. *American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 13, 6-9.

6. Durdon Rasulmuxamedova. (2023). TOPICS AND ISSUES RAISED IN THE WORKS OF GAFUR GULYAM. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 18, 68-70. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbml/article/view/1961>

7. Turabaeva, Lazzat K., and Nodir N. Ramazanov. "SPEECH CULTURE AND LANGUAGE PURITY." *American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research* 12 (2023): 153-156

8. Расулмухамедова, Д. 2021. Выражение идеи свободы в творчестве Гафура Гуляма. *Общество и инновации*. 2, 3 (июн. 2021), 56–61. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss3-pp56-61>.

9. Якубовна, Г. 2021. Лексические нормы юридического языка. *Общество и инновации*. 2, 3 (июн. 2021), 62–67. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss3-pp62-67>.

10. Зиямухамедова Ш. Т. СТРУКТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОКОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ ТЕРМИНОВ В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ // *International Journal of Innovative Technologies in Social Science*. 2019. №4 (16). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/strukturnyy-analiz-informatsionnokommunikatsionnyh-terminov-v-uzbekskom-yazyke> (дата обращения: 06.02.2024).

11. Хашимова Д. У., Ниязова Н. Ж. О ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОМ ИССЛЕДОВАНИИ ЛАКУН В УСЛОВИЯХ ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА С ДРУГИМИ ЯЗЫКАМИ // *Актуальные проблемы аккультурации в контексте преподавания русского языка как иностранного*. – 2022. – С. 74-83.

12. Niyazova N. Modern methods of teaching russian as a foreign language //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 5. – С. 358-362.

13. Амина Рустамовна Фаттахова АВТОРСКОЕ «Я» В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ АЛИСЫ ГАНИЕВОЙ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/avtorskoe-ya-v-tvorchestve-alisy-ganievoy> (дата обращения: 06.02.2024).

14. Umida Ramazonovna PULATOVA. (2023). ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE APPLICATION OF CREATIVE TASKS (BASED ON WORKS OF FICTION). World Bulletin of Management and Law, 18, 71-75. Retrieved from <https://www.scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbml/article/view/1962>

15. Бозорова, Н. П. (2020). 9. БАДИИЙ АСАР ҚАХРАМОНИ ТАҚДИРИДА ХУЖЖАТЛАР ЎРНИ. Образование и инновационные исследования / международный научно-методический журнал, (2), 71-75.

16. Рамазанов, Нодир. "Право и литература: правовой дискурс в литературе и перспективы трактовки правовых текстов художественными методами." *Review of law sciences* 4. Спецвыпуск (2020): 180-188.

17. Ramazonov, N., et al. "ON THE RELATIONSHIP OF THE SUFI CONCEPT OF FAQR (رفق) AND THE CHARACTERS IN THE LYRIC POETRY OF ALISHER NAVOI." *湖南大学学报(自然科学版)* 48.8 (2021).

18. Ramazanov, Nadir. "Поэтическая интерпретация концепта факр в лирике Алишера Навои." *Theoretical & Applied Science* 7 (2019): 344-347.

19. Mirzakarimovna, R. D. (2022). KONSTITUTSIYAVIY ISLOHOTLAR–HUQUQIY TARAQQIYOT GAROVI. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(3), 116-119.

20. Raxmonova, D. (2022, September). RULES OF DISPUTES IN THE FIELD OF JURISPRUDENCE. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND

PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS" (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 50-54).

21. Babadjanova, N. (2020). ISAJON SULTONNING «YUSUF VA ZULAYHO» HIKOYASI TAHLILI. Materiali konferentsiya MTND , 76-78.

